

DOES HIGHER EDUCATION GROWTH INCREASE ECONOMIC GROWTH?

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Abstract

This study seeks to establish the existence of a causal relationship between higher education and economic growth in Uganda, with special focus on the categories of discipline, gender and level of higher education graduates. The study employs the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to establish the interrelationship between these two variables from 1985 to 2017. The results of this study reveal the existence of a long run but not short run effect of higher education on the growth of GDP. The results show a unidirectional causality that was established from GDP to: total graduates; male and female graduates, Arts and Science graduates, as well as postgraduate and undergraduates. The impact of economic growth on higher education was higher for the males compared to female graduates; graduates from science disciplines compared to the Arts, and undergraduates compared to postgraduates. Worth noting is the vital role of GCF as a link between the two variables of Growth and Higher education which was revealed in the findings.

Key Words: *Graduates, Gross Domestic product, Uganda, Vector Error Correction Model.*

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between economic growth and higher education is debatable in the literature. Some studies have established a positive causality where: (i) economic growth influences higher education (Yurtkuran & Terzi, 2015) in Turkey (ii) higher education influences economic growth for example, in Portugal (Rosario, Costa & Silva, 2018), Nigeria (Eregha, Irughe & Edefe, 2018), India (Mehta & Tandel, 2017), Sweden (Obradovic & Lojanica, 2016) and Greece (Mallick & Dash, 2015); (iii) a bi-directional relationship between economic growth and higher education for example, in the Republic of Czech and Romania (Oancea, Pospisil & Dragoescu, 2017), in five MENA countries such as, Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia and Turkey (Bouhari & Soussi, 2017) and Nigeria (Ogunbunmi & Abiola, 2017). Other studies have concluded that the relationship

between economic growth and higher education is either negative such as, in Cote d'Ivoire (Kouton, 2018), in a cross-country study 49 countries (Eggoh, Houeninvo & Sossou, 2015) in Sri Lanka (Vijesandiran & Vinayagathan, 2015) or insignificant in South Africa (Malangeni & Phiri, 2018), in Indonesia (Rizal & Nurruhwati, 2018), in Ethiopia (Borojo & Yushi, 2015) and in a study across the globe (Valero & Reenen, 2018). This evidence was noted mainly in the studies of developed countries but had scarce literature among developing countries.

The empirical findings of a positive relationship between higher education and economic growth were established mainly using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Panel data methodologies despite of their limitations (Ugrinowitsch, Fellingham & Ricard, 2004). For instance, the OLS methodology is limited in handling time series data while the panel approach generalizes the characteristics and empirical findings since it is based on data from several countries. Furthermore, panel studies compare countries based on an assumption that they are all at the same level of production, technology and growth frontier which is usually not the case. Thus, the findings from such studies may not be applied directly to each individual country and others elsewhere. In order to overcoming the challenges of OLS data, the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag model (ARDL), a time series methodology was adopted to handle small sample size data (Haug, 2002). The ARDL methodology uses both current and lagged values of higher education and economic growth. However, it is questionable whether the current enrolments or graduates of higher education contribute to the economic growth in light of the high graduate unemployment with an emphasis of developing countries such as, Uganda.

On investigating the causality, it was noted that higher education was assessed based on enrolments and public expenditure of higher education institutions. However, use of students' enrolments as a measure of higher education is questionable because enrolees do not immediately contribute to the labour market (Gyimah-Brempong & Paddison, 2006; Bokana & Akinola, 2017). In addition, the overall number of enrolees in higher education hides the contribution of individual categories of graduates to economic growth. For example, it is crucial to establish whether gender differences of graduates affect the economic growth, or there exists any disparity between Arts and Science graduates; and between undergraduates and postgraduates, and the economic growth. For countries whose investment in higher education has greatly been privatized, it is more likely that government expenditure on education would be under estimated.

Therefore, this study uses graduates disaggregated by gender, discipline (Arts vs. Sciences) and award level (undergraduate vs. postgraduate) as a measure of higher education, whose relationship is investigated with the economic growth of Uganda. In addition, this study adopted a methodology based on lagged values of higher education to investigate the changes in current economic growth. This paper is structured into three sections, namely; the case of Uganda, methodology, empirical results and policy recommendations.

Higher Education in Uganda

The higher education sector of Uganda draws its origin from the establishment of Makerere University in 1922, as a technical college, with a population of 14 students. In 1964/1965 student enrolment at Makerere was 1,331, which grew to 1,805 in 1967/1968. By 1970/1971 about 2,638 students were enrolled at Makerere (Musisi & Muwanga 2003). In 1980's the student enrolments had grown to 2500 (Nannyonjo, Najjumba Mulindwa & Usher, 2009). Currently, the higher education sector comprises of three sub-sectors namely; Universities, Other Degree awarding Institutions (ODI) and Other Tertiary Institutions (OTI). The universities offer degrees, diplomas and certificates; the ODI specialise in only one area of study but still award degrees, diplomas and certificates; while the OTI offer only diplomas and certificates. There are 11 public and 44 private universities; 9 ODI and 163 OTI in Uganda (NCHE, 2016; MES, 2017). According to the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE) the overall enrolment of students in the higher education sector of Uganda had grown to 183,985 (26.4%) and 198,066 (14.2%) in 2010 and 2011 respectively (NCHE, 2013). By 2017, the total enrolment in the higher education sector was 258,866 students which studied both day and evening programmes, of which 114,314 (56%) were males while 114,552 (44%) were females. The university sub-sector is estimated to enrol about 186,412 (72%) students, of which 44% and 56% are females and males respectively (MES, 2017; UBOS, 2017). According to the NCHE (2016) about 94% of the students who enrol in the sector are able to complete their courses, graduate and are released into the labour market.

Economic Growth in Uganda

The economic growth of Uganda, measured as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), is the contribution from three major sectors namely; agriculture, industry/manufacturing and service sector. In general, since independence, Uganda's economic growth has been fluctuating (Mwakikagile, 2009), which has questioned the contribution of higher education. In 1981, Uganda embarked on an

economic recovery program that attracted foreign aid. However, these efforts were annulled by the civil war in 1984 that led to high inflation, reduced growth and an economy that was termed as one that had collapsed (Collier & Reinikka, 2001). From 1986, the economy grew following recovery from war and various economic reforms (Collier & Reinikka, 2001), which led to an annual GDP growth rate of about 6.1% in Uganda.

This was followed by low productivity and limited capital accumulation due to the flight of Asian entrepreneurs from Uganda (Berthelemy & Soderling, 2001). In 1990, there was a programme to transform and liberalise Uganda's economy, with assistance from the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF), to one whose growth depended mainly on the private sector (Kasekende, 2007). This included structural adjustment programs that were seen to be ambitious in Africa (Balihuta & Sen, 2001). Annual GDP growth rate grew to 6.7% (World Bank, 2018). However, the growth slowed down thereafter. By 2017, GDP was approximately 26.39 billion US dollars (World Bank, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized annual secondary data for the period 1985 to 2017, was obtained from two major sources: data on economic growth, measured as GDP, Gross Capital Formation (GCF) and Total Labour Force (TLF) was obtained from the 2018 World Bank Indicators data base. Capital and labour were incorporated due to theoretical foundations of the Cobb-Douglas theory (Solow, 1956, 1957; Mankiw et al., 1992). The second source was the Academic Registrar's offices of the oldest three and largest public Universities in Uganda namely; Makerere University, Mbarara University of Science and Technology and Kyambogo University. Here data on the number of graduates, a measure of higher education, was obtained. These institutions take the largest share of student enrolments of higher education in the country (NCHE, 2016). In this analysis, quarterly time series data was used. The annual data obtained for 33 years (from 1985 to 2017) was quarterised using the quarterising tool in EVIEWS to obtain 132 observations that were used for the analysis. This was done to increase the number of data points for better analysis.

In the investigation of the relationship between economic growth and higher education disaggregated into gender, award level & discipline, the study had four major simultaneous model systems of equations. The first investigated the impact of total graduates, the second investigated the impact of gender of graduates, the third, investigated the effect of award level of graduates;

and the fourth investigated the impact of graduates' discipline. In this investigation, the regressions borrow from the augmented Cobb-Douglas production function. The analysis was based on five major steps:

First, the study examines the existence of stationarity of variables: GDP, higher education graduates, GCF, and Total Labour force. To test this, the study used the Augmented Dicker Fuller test. The next step was to obtain the optimal lag length. The determination of optimal lag length was done by use of the Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC) and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ). The study further tests for co-integration of variables, to determine whether the variables have a long run relationship. To analyse this, the study used the Johansen-Juselius (1990) approach. The fourth step was to obtain the coefficient estimates and significance from the regressions. In the analysis, where co-integration was found, the VECM was applied. The fifth step was to test for the direction and nature of short run causality between economic growth and higher education graduates, using the Wald test (Hondroyiannis, Lolos, & Papapetro, 2005). This was to see whether the lagged values of the explanatory variables jointly cause the corresponding dependent variables.

Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

A Vector error correction model (VECM), is a type of the VAR model, which is specially used when variables are non-stationary, and are Co-integrated. The VECM is preferred because it adjusts for both short run and long run dynamics (Juselius, 1991; Johansen, 1995). The VECM is represented in equation (1)

$$\Delta x_t = v + \Pi x_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Phi_i^* \Delta x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where $\Pi = -(I - \Phi_1 - \Phi_2 - \dots - \Phi_p) = -\Phi(1)$; I is an identity matrix; $\Phi_j^* = -\sum_{i=j+1}^p \Phi_i$; $j=1, \dots, p-1$

Where Rank (Π) = m ; $0 < m < k$; Π (a $k \times k$ matrix) is considered equal to $\alpha\beta'$, with α being a $(k \times m)$ matrix of Eigen values, m , that are co-integrating vectors; and β being a $(k \times m)$ ' matrix of eigen values m , that are adjusting vectors. Πx_{t-1} represents the lagged error-correction term that explains the long run relationship while $\sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Phi_i^* \Delta x_{t-i}$ explains the short run relationship between the variables; $i=1, \dots, k-1$ is the number of optimal lags; Δ is the first difference; Φ_i^* is a matrix of coefficients that explain the short run dynamics in the system.

In a VECM form, which is an extension of the VAR model after including an error correction value that is lagged a Seemingly Unrelated Regressions (SUR), is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln GDP_t &= \delta_1 + ECT_1 + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{11p} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{12p} \Delta \ln GCF_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{13p} \Delta \ln LFP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{14p} \Delta \ln EDUC_{t-p} + \varphi_1 \hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + v_{1t} \\ \Delta \ln GCF_t &= \delta_1 + ECT_2 + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{21p} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{22p} \Delta \ln GCF_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{23p} \Delta \ln LFP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{24p} \Delta \ln EDUC_{t-p} + \varphi_2 \hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + v_{2t} \\ \Delta \ln LFP_t &= \delta_1 + ECT_3 + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{31p} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{32p} \Delta \ln GCF_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{33p} \Delta \ln LFP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{34p} \Delta \ln EDUC_{t-p} + \varphi_3 \hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + v_{3t} \\ \Delta \ln EDUC_t &= \delta_1 + ECT_4 + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{41p} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{42p} \Delta \ln GCF_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{43p} \Delta \ln LFP_{t-p} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_{44p} \Delta \ln EDUC_{t-p} + \varphi_4 \hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + v_{4t} \end{aligned}$$

Where Δ first difference of a variable, k is the lag length that is optimal, $\hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1}$ are error terms.

RESULTS

Stationarity Test

The results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test unit root test are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Results for the Stationarity Tests for Variables

Levels	Level		First Difference	
	Value	P-value	Value	P-value
LnGDP	-1.084253	0.7208	-9.436831	0.0000
LnGCF	-1.411906	0.5746	-10.68004	0.0000
lnTLF	-1.849760	0.3551	-11.05354	0.0000
LnTotal	-1.030832	0.7409	-11.68099	0.0000
lnUnder	-0.924801	0.7776	-11.85071	0.0000
lnPost	-1.749371	0.4041	-14.29884	0.0000
LnSci	-1.122512	0.7056	-13.81536	0.0000
LnARTS	-0.988892	0.7560	-12.96655	0.0000
LnFemale	-1.026274	0.7426	-11.95629	0.0000
LnMale	-1.062235	0.7292	-11.34694	0.0000

Note: Estimate were obtained using the Augmented Dickey Fuller Tests

From Table 1, it was observed that all variables were non stationary at level but became stationary at first difference ($p < 0.01$).

Optimal Lag Selection

The optimal lag was selected by getting the lag that was most selected by the HQ, SIC, AIC, and LR lag selection criteria. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of the Optimal Lag Selection

Model	Lag	LR	AIC	SIC	HQ
LNGDP=f(LNGCF, LNLFP, LNTotal)	0	2.65e-05	0.813263	0.901495	0.849114
	1	6.88e-08	-5.140011	-4.698852	-4.960754
	2	2.35e-08*	-6.216357*	-5.422271*	-5.893694*
LNGDP=f(LNGCF,LNLFP,LNARTS,LNSCI)	0	2.31e-06	1.212818	1.323108	1.257633
	1	4.53e-09	-5.024187	-4.362448	-4.755300
	2	1.46e-09*	-6.157662*	-4.944474*	-5.664703*
LNGDP=f(LNGCF,LNLFP,LNMALE,LNFEM)	0	1.31e-06	0.645918	0.756208	0.690732
	1	1.45e-09	-6.165785	-5.504046	-5.896898
	2	4.57e-10*	-7.318799*	-6.105611*	-6.825840*
LNGDP=f(LNGCF,LNLFP,LNPOST,LNUND)	0	1.50e-06	0.779688	0.889978	0.824503
	1	2.84e-09	-5.489342	-4.827603	-5.220456
	2	9.86e-10*	-6.550434*	-5.337247*	-6.057475*

Note. Sequential modified LR test statistic (LR), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ)

From Table 2, the majority choice out of the LR, AIC, SIC, and HQ statistics revealed that the optimal lag for all the four models is 2.

Co-integration of Variables

The results for the co-integration test are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of the Co-integration Test

Regression Model	Data Trend:	None	None	Linear	Linear	Quadratic
		Test	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept
		Type	No Intercept	No Intercept	Trend	Trend
LNGDP	Trace	1	1	1	1	1
LNGCF LNTLF LNTotal	Max-Eig	1	1	1	1	1
LNGDP	Trace	1	1	1	1	1
	Max-Eig	1	1	1	1	1

LNGCF LNTLF LNMALE							
LNFEMALE							
LNGDP	Trace	1	1	1	1	1	1
LNGCF LNTLF LNARTS	Max-Eig	1	1	1	1	1	1
LNSCI							
LNGDP	Trace	1	1	1	1	1	1
LNGCF LNTLF LNPOST	Max-Eig	1	1	1	1	1	1
LNUNDER							

Note: Gross Domestic product (GDP), Gross capital Formation (GCF), Total labour force (TLF), Total graduates (Total), female graduates (Female), male graduates (Male), postgraduates (Post), undergraduates (Under), graduates from the arts (ARTS) and science disciplines (SCI).

From Table 3, shows that there is one co-integrating equation for all the four model systems. This implies that there is a long run relationship between GDP,GCF,TLF, Total graduates; GDP,GCF,TLF, males, females graduates; GDP,GCF,TLF, Arts, Science graduates; GDP,GCF,TLF, postgraduates, undergraduates. In other words, these variables are co-integrated. This test however, does not show the direction and size of the causal relationship. This was done using regression analyses (VECM) and Wald tests.

Estimation Results for the VECM Analyses

All the variables in the four models were co-integrated, hence a VECM was used.

Model one: Total Graduates

The short run and long run dynamics of the VECM regression estimates, for the first system of equations with variables Gross Domestic Product (GDP),Gross Capital Formation (GCF), Labour Force Participation (LFP), and Total graduates), are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Results for the Estimation of Total Graduates

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1
LNGDP(-1)	1.000000
LNGCF(-1)	-1.802709 (0.24376) [-7.39557]
LNTLF(-1)	5.563148

	(0.97947)
	[5.67975]
LNTOTAL(-1)	-0.523080
	(0.20058)
	[-2.60788]
C	-41.87003

Error Correction:	D(LNGDP)	D(LNGCF)	D(LNTLF)	D(LNTOTAL)
CointEq1	-0.056065	-0.197447***	-0.076677***	-0.048980
	(0.04465)	(0.05616)	(0.02371)	(0.06915)
	[-1.25574]	[-3.51552]	[-3.23328]	[-0.70833]
D(LNGDP(-1))	-1.176499***	0.153572	-0.731970***	-0.735982***
	(0.17696)	(0.22261)	(0.09400)	(0.27407)
	[-6.64835]	[0.68986]	[-7.78726]	[-2.68536]
D(LNGDP(-2))	0.021463	0.956157***	0.041256	0.177862
	(0.27927)	(0.35131)	(0.14834)	(0.43252)
	[0.07685]	[2.72170]	[0.27813]	[0.41122]
D(LNGCF(-1))	0.694508***	-0.756152***	0.676271***	0.709343***
	(0.15414)	(0.19390)	(0.08187)	(0.23873)
	[4.50569]	[-3.89962]	[8.25989]	[2.97135]
D(LNGCF(-2))	-0.153934	-1.099409***	-0.083039	-0.204127
	(0.27371)	(0.34432)	(0.14539)	(0.42391)
	[-0.56240]	[-3.19298]	[-0.57116]	[-0.48153]
D(LNTLF(-1))	0.480924	1.259004***	0.133583	0.784467
	(0.33559)	(0.42216)	(0.17825)	(0.51974)
	[1.43309]	[2.98231]	[0.74941]	[1.50934]
D(LNTLF(-2))	0.553034	0.095716	0.482059*	0.697061
	(0.53361)	(0.67126)	(0.28343)	(0.82644)
	[1.03640]	[0.14259]	[1.70077]	[0.84345]
D(LNTOTAL(-1))	-0.035970	-0.073784	-0.055904	-0.692095***
	(0.06582)	(0.08280)	(0.03496)	(0.10194)
	[-0.54651]	[-0.89113]	[-1.59906]	[-6.78938]
D(LNTOTAL(-2))	-0.002744	-0.012061	-0.017563	-0.291743***
	(0.06501)	(0.08178)	(0.03453)	(0.10069)
	[-0.04220]	[-0.14748]	[-0.50860]	[-2.89744]
C	0.009934	0.042100	1.85E-06	0.020265

(0.01188)	(0.01495)	(0.00631)	(0.01841)
[0.83583]	[2.81590]	[0.00029]	[1.10093]

Note: Figures denote the coefficients, standard errors(), and t-statistics[]. Δ denotes first difference,-1 denotes lag 1,-2 denotes lag 2, ln denotes natural Logarithm transformation. *, ** and *** means significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

From Table 4, the co-integrating variables are shown in the equation 4.1 as follows:

$$\text{LNGDP} (-1) = 1.802709\text{LNGCF} (-1) - 5.563148\text{LNTLF} (-1) + 0.523080\text{LNTOTAL} (-1) + 41.87003 \quad (1)$$

The constant value of 41.87003 in equation 4.1 implies that the variables adjust towards equilibrium in the long run at the rate of 41.9 %.

Also, from Table 4 shows GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on GDP, while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on GDP. GDP lagged twice and TLF lagged once have a positive and significant effect on GCF, while GCF lagged once has a negative and significant effect on GCF. GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on TLF, yet GCF lagged once and TLF lagged twice have a positive and significant effect on TLF. GDP lagged once, and Total graduates have a negative and significant effect on Total graduates; while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on Total graduates. In other words the regression coefficients show that there is a short run unidirectional relationship from GDP to Total graduates.

Model Two: Gender of Graduates

The results for gender of graduates are given in Table 5.

From Table 5, the co-integrating variables are shown in the equation 2 as follows:

$$\text{LNGDP} (-1) = 1.641199\text{LNGCF} (-1) - 4.514596\text{LNTLF} (-1) + 0.283600 \text{LNMALE} (-1) + 0.104430\text{LNFEMALE} (-1) + 34.93734 \quad (2)$$

The constant value of 34.93734 in equation 2 implies that the variables adjust towards equilibrium in the long run at the rate of 34.9%.

Also, from Table 5, GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on GDP, while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on GDP. GDP lagged twice and TL (2F lagged once have a positive and significant effect on GCF, while GCF has a negative and significant effect on GCF. GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on TLF, yet GCF lagged once and

TLF lagged twice have a positive and significant effect on TLF. GDP lagged once, and male graduates lagged once have a negative and significant effect on male graduates; while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on male graduates. GDP lagged once, and female graduates have a negative and significant effect on female graduates; while GCF lagged once and TLF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on female graduates. In other words the regression coefficients show that there is a short run unidirectional relationship from GDP to both male and female graduates.

Table 5: Regression Results for Gender Graduates

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1				
LNGDP(-1)	1.000000				
LNGCF(-1)	-1.641199 (0.19284) [-8.51060]				
LNTLF(-1)	4.514596 (0.77647) [5.81423]				
LNMALE(-1)	-0.283600 (0.24358) [-1.16430]				
LNFEMALE(-1)	-0.104430 (0.17466) [-0.59789]				
C	-34.93734				
Error Correction:	D(LNGDP)	D(LNGCF)	D(LNTLF)	D(LNMALE)	D(LNFEMALE)
CointEq1	-0.076360 (0.05578) [-1.36905]				
D(LNGDP(-1))	-1.150342*** (0.18193) [-6.32299]				
D(LNGDP(-2))	0.029316 (0.28158) [0.10412]				
D(LNGCF(-1))	0.667671*** (0.16071) [4.15451]				
D(LNGCF(-2))	-0.169918 (0.22894) [0.87829]				
	-0.248349*** (0.07019) [-3.53831]				
	0.201077 (0.22894) [0.87829]				
	-0.698937*** (0.09657) [-7.23789]				
	-0.773532*** (0.28543) [-2.71004]				
	-0.575290** (0.27215) [-2.11389]				
	0.973323*** (0.35434) [2.74687]				
	0.056706 (0.14946) [0.37941]				
	0.114863 (0.44177) [0.26001]				
	0.309373 (0.42121) [0.73449]				
	0.644556*** (0.08530) [7.55607]				
	0.726392*** (0.25214) [2.88092]				
	0.575248** (0.24040) [2.39284]				
	-0.101756 (0.105489) [-0.96441]				

	(0.27720)	(0.34883)	(0.14713)	(0.43490)	(0.41465)
	[-0.61299]	[-3.22097]	[-0.69159]	[-0.24256]	[-0.74192]
D(LNTRLF(-1))	0.473594	1.239188***	0.132063	0.719703	1.082316**
	(0.34318)	(0.43186)	(0.18215)	(0.53841)	(0.51336)
	[1.38003]	[2.86944]	[0.72500]	[1.33671]	[2.10832]
D(LNTRLF(-2))	0.618518	0.202951	0.538786*	0.581916	0.959369
	(0.55960)	(0.70421)	(0.29703)	(0.87797)	(0.83710)
	[1.10528]	[0.28820]	[1.81391]	[0.66280]	[1.14606]
D(LNMALE(-1))	-0.077668	-0.097842	-0.023112	-0.533477***	0.100551
	(0.08783)	(0.11052)	(0.04662)	(0.13780)	(0.13138)
	[-0.88431]	[-0.88525]	[-0.49577]	[-3.87150]	[0.76533]
D(LNMALE(-2))	-0.009540	0.015250	0.000543	-0.177556	0.095131
	(0.08801)	(0.11076)	(0.04672)	(0.13809)	(0.13166)
	[-0.10839]	[0.13769]	[0.01162]	[-1.28583]	[0.72255]
D(LNFEMALE(-1))	0.043436	0.016865	-0.022821	-0.110690	-0.840404***
	(0.09246)	(0.11635)	(0.04907)	(0.14506)	(0.13830)
	[0.46980]	[0.14496]	[-0.46503]	[-0.76309]	[-6.07650]
D(LNFEMALE(-2))	0.004067	-0.042695	-0.023217	-0.098986	-0.439329***
	(0.09411)	(0.11843)	(0.04995)	(0.14765)	(0.14078)
	[0.04321]	[-0.36051]	[-0.46477]	[-0.67040]	[-3.12068]
C	0.009710	0.042528***	0.000465	0.015875	0.035277*
	(0.01206)	(0.01517)	(0.00640)	(0.01891)	(0.01803)
	[0.80539]	[2.80328]	[0.07262]	[0.83931]	[1.95613]

Note: Figures denote the coefficients, standard errors(), and t-statistics[]. Δ denotes first difference,-1 denotes lag 1,-2 denotes lag 2, ln denotes natural Logarithm transformation. *, ** and *** means significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Model Three: Award Level of Graduates

The findings for Award level of Graduates are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Regression Results for Level of Graduates

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1
LNGDP(-1)	1.000000
LNGCF(-1)	-1.648915
	(0.17788)
	[-9.26998]
LNTRLF(-1)	3.735959
	(0.79613)
	[4.69266]
LNPOST(-1)	0.304764

(0.19406)
 [1.57048]
 LNUNDER(-1) -0.338558
 (0.13418)
 [-2.52308]
 C -29.96233

Error Correction:	D(LNGDP)	D(LNGCF)	D(LNTLF)	D(LNPOST)	D(LNUNDER)
CointEq1	-0.060950 (0.06011) [-1.01392]	-0.251046*** (0.07579) [-3.31226]	-0.099629*** (0.03187) [-3.12594]	-0.180274* (0.09636) [-1.87088]	-0.057387 (0.09695) [-0.59193]
D(LNGDP(-1))	-1.176862*** (0.18735) [-6.28151]	0.204023 (0.23622) [0.86369]	-0.705376*** (0.09933) [-7.10106]	-0.516811* (0.30032) [-1.72089]	-0.706013** (0.30216) [-2.33656]
D(LNGDP(-2))	0.020311 (0.28581) [0.07107]	1.005704*** (0.36036) [2.79080]	0.062502 (0.15154) [0.41245]	0.212931 (0.45814) [0.46477]	0.190710 (0.46095) [0.41373]
D(LNGCF(-1))	0.707933*** (0.16693) [4.24091]	-0.793844*** (0.21047) [-3.77175]	0.658143*** (0.08851) [7.43621]	0.517238* (0.26758) [1.93304]	0.702606*** (0.26922) [2.60978]
D(LNGCF(-2))	-0.142177 (0.28123) [-0.50555]	-1.129457*** (0.35459) [-3.18524]	-0.096581 (0.14911) [-0.64772]	-0.205362 (0.45080) [-0.45555]	-0.199776 (0.45357) [-0.44046]
D(LNTLF(-1))	0.418849 (0.32357) [1.29446]	1.129370*** (0.40797) [2.76828]	0.087354 (0.17156) [0.50919]	1.158799** (0.51866) [2.23421]	0.714772 (0.52184) [1.36970]
D(LNTLF(-2))	0.495552 (0.53235) [0.93087]	-0.032618 (0.67121) [-0.04860]	0.448050 (0.28225) [1.58741]	0.949464 (0.85333) [1.11266]	0.673353 (0.85857) [0.78428]
D(LNPOST(-1))	-0.017342 (0.06391) [-0.27133]	0.029133 (0.08058) [0.36152]	-0.008424 (0.03389) [-0.24860]	-0.879420*** (0.10245) [-8.58397]	-0.076194 (0.10308) [-0.73919]
D(LNPOST(-2))	-0.010444 (0.06330) [-0.16500]	0.007279 (0.07981) [0.09121]	-0.005646 (0.03356) [-0.16823]	-0.499255*** (0.10146) [-4.92061]	-0.064874 (0.10208) [-0.63549]
D(LNUNDER(-1))	-0.011240 (0.07053) [-0.15936]	-0.047444 (0.08893) [-0.53352]	-0.030924 (0.03739) [-0.82696]	0.037360 (0.11306) [0.33046]	-0.625341*** (0.11375) [-5.49753]
D(LNUNDER(-2))	0.010085 (0.07015) [0.14376]	0.019044 (0.08845) [0.21532]	-0.003659 (0.03719) [-0.09837]	0.060705 (0.11245) [0.53986]	-0.242661** (0.11314) [-2.14485]
C	0.009469 (0.01200) [0.78921]	0.041475*** (0.01513) [2.74169]	-0.000114 (0.00636) [-0.01796]	0.023662 (0.01923) [1.23034]	0.021500 (0.01935) [1.11111]

Note: Figures denote the coefficients, standard errors(), and t-statistics[]. Δ denotes first difference, -1 denotes lag 1, -2 denotes lag 2, ln denotes natural Logarithm transformation. *, ** and *** means significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

From Table 6, the co-integrating variables are shown in the equation 4.1 as follows:

$$\text{LNGDP} (-1) = 1.648915\text{LNGCF} (-1) - 3.735959\text{LNTLF} (-1) - 0.304764\text{LNPOST} (-1) + 0.338558\text{LNUNDER} (-1) + 29.96233 \quad (3)$$

The constant value of 29.96233 in equation 3 implies that the variables adjust towards equilibrium in the long run at the rate of 30%.

Also, from Table 6, GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on GDP, while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on GDP. GDP lagged twice and TLF lagged once have a positive and significant effect on GCF, while GCF has a negative and significant effect on GCF. GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on TLF, yet GCF lagged once and TLF lagged twice have a positive and significant effect on TLF. GDP lagged once, and postgraduates lagged once have a negative and significant effect on postgraduates; while GCF and TLF lagged and has a positive and significant effect on postgraduates. GDP lagged once, and undergraduates have a negative and significant effect on undergraduates; while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on science graduates. In other words the regression coefficients show that there is a short run unidirectional relationship from GDP to both Post and undergraduates.

Model Four: Discipline of Graduates

The estimation results for the category of the discipline of Graduates are shown in Table 7.

From Table 7, the co-integrating variables are shown in the equation 4.1 as follows:

$$\text{LNGDP} (-1) = 1.978787\text{LNGCF} (-1) - 6.563085\text{LNTLF} (-1) + 0.232021 \text{LNARTS} (-1) + 0.426573\text{LNSCI} (-1) + 49.04577 \quad (4)$$

The constant value of 49.04577 in equation 4 implies that the variables adjust towards equilibrium in the long run at the rate of 49%.

Also from Table 7, GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on GDP, while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on GDP. GDP lagged twice and TLF lagged once have a positive and significant effect on GCF, while GCF has a negative and significant effect on

GCF. GDP lagged once has a negative and significant effect on TLF, yet GCF lagged once and TLF lagged twice have a positive and significant effect on TLF. GDP lagged once, and Arts graduates lagged once have a negative and significant effect on Arts graduates; while GCF lagged once has a positive and significant effect on Arts graduates. GDP lagged once, and science graduates have a negative and significant effect on science graduates; while GCF lagged once and TLF lagged once, plus science graduates have a positive and significant effect on science graduates. In other words the regression coefficients show that there is a short run unidirectional relationship from GDP to both arts and science graduates.

Table 7: Regression Results for Discipline of Graduates

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1				
LNGDP(-1)	1.000000				
LNGCF(-1)	-1.978787 (0.28832) [-6.86328]				
LNLFP(-1)	6.563085 (1.31551) [4.98900]				
LNARTS(-1)	-0.232021 (0.20633) [-1.12450]				
LNSCI(-1)	-0.426573 (0.35320) [-1.20773]				
C	-49.04577				
Error Correction:	D(LNGDP)	D(LNGCF)	D(LNTLF)	D(LNARTS)	D(LNSCI)
CointEq1	-0.042961 (0.03920) [-1.09607]	-0.164220*** (0.04940) [-3.32428]	-0.064158*** (0.02072) [-3.09693]	-0.013937 (0.07109) [-0.19605]	-0.069727 (0.06154) [-1.13311]
D(LNGDP(-1))	-1.211144*** (0.17917) [-6.75987]	0.117750 (0.22581) [0.52145]	-0.765699*** (0.09470) [-8.08577]	-0.687189** (0.32495) [-2.11475]	-0.892206*** (0.28129) [-3.17187]
D(LNGDP(-2))	0.008479 (0.28922) [0.02932]	0.981568*** (0.36452) [2.69276]	0.020741 (0.15287) [0.13568]	0.356523 (0.52456) [0.67966]	-0.224030 (0.45407) [-0.49338]
D(LNGCF(-1))	0.719166*** (0.15349) [4.68547]	-0.724793*** (0.19345) [-3.74669]	0.694605*** (0.08113) [8.56214]	0.722388*** (0.27838) [2.59498]	0.733368*** (0.24097) [3.04336]
D(LNGCF(-2))	-0.141132 (0.28097) [-0.50230]	-1.104740*** (0.35412) [-3.11968]	-0.066548 (0.14850) [-0.44812]	-0.316159 (0.50959) [-0.62042]	0.121727 (0.44111) [0.27595]
D(LNTLF(-1))	0.488673 (0.35359) [1.38202]	1.316486*** (0.44565) [2.95408]	0.157152 (0.18689) [0.84089]	0.629462 (0.64130) [0.98153]	1.096772** (0.55513) [1.97570]
D(LNTLF(-2))	0.572873 (0.56049) [1.02210]	0.048259 (0.70641) [0.06832]	0.498020* (0.29624) [1.68114]	0.687980 (1.01654) [0.67679]	0.605840 (0.87995) [0.68850]
D(LNARTS(-1))	0.002852 (0.05249) [0.05434]	-0.032889 (0.06615) [-0.49717]	0.004878 (0.02774) [0.17585]	-0.729805*** (0.09520) [-7.66637]	0.109045 (0.08240) [1.32330]
D(LNARTS(-2))	-0.008053 (0.05338)	-0.023868 (0.06727)	-0.001954 (0.02821)	-0.368752*** (0.09681)	0.104706 (0.08380)

	[-0.15087]	[-0.35480]	[-0.06927]	[-3.80912]	[1.24948]
D(LNSCI(-1))	-0.051745 (0.05979)	-0.064891 (0.07535)	-0.067877** (0.03160)	0.017622 (0.10843)	-0.885206*** (0.09386)
	[-0.86548]	[-0.86116]	[-2.14801]	[0.16251]	[-9.43069]
D(LNSCI(-2))	-0.015863 (0.05946)	0.017044 (0.07495)	-0.028432 (0.03143)	0.033523 (0.10785)	-0.463529*** (0.09336)
	[-0.26676]	[0.22742]	[-0.90462]	[0.31083]	[-4.96506]
C	0.010112 (0.01205)	0.042027*** (0.01519)	0.000245 (0.00637)	0.019740 (0.02185)	0.027299 (0.01892)
	[0.83931]	[2.76759]	[0.03844]	[0.90335]	[1.44319]

Note: Figures denote the coefficients, standard errors(), and t-statistics[]. Δ denotes first difference,-1 denotes lag 1,-2 denotes lag 2, ln denotes natural Logarithm transformation. *, ** and *** means significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Causality Tests: Wald Test

The results of the Wald test for model one is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Combined Results of the Wald Test for the Four Systems

Model	Null Hypotheses	P value	Decision at 5%	Conclusion
LNGDP=f(LNGCF, LN TLF, LNTotal)	Ho:C(8)=C(9)=0	0.8315	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from Total graduates to GDP.
	Ho: C(32)=C(33)=0	0.0027	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to Total graduates.
LNGDP LNGCF LNTLF LNMALE LNFEMALE	Ho:C(8)=C(9)=0	0.6316	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from male graduates to GDP.
	Ho:C(10)=C(11)=0	0.8689	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from female graduates to GDP.
	Ho:C(38)=C(39)=0	0.0033	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to male graduates.
	Ho:C(50)=C(51)=0	0.0095	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to female graduates.

LNGDP LNGCF LNTLF LNARTS LNSCI	Ho:C(8)=C(9)=0	0.9762	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from Arts graduates to GDP.
	Ho:C(10)=C(11)=0	0.6652	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from Science graduates to GDP.
	Ho:C(38)=C(39)=0	0.0115	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to Arts graduates.
	Ho:C(50)=C(51)=0	0.0025	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to Science graduates.
LNGDP LNGCF LNTLF LNPOST LNUNDER	Ho:C(8)=C(9)=0	0.9638	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from postgraduates. GDP.
	Ho:C(10)=C(11)=0	0.9558	Accept Ho	There is no short run causality running from undergraduates to GDP.
	Ho:C(38)=C(39)=0	0.0563	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to postgraduates.
	Ho:C(50)=C(51)=0	0.0087	Reject Ho	There is short run causality running from GDP to undergraduates.

Note: Coefficients are denoted by symbols $c(1), \dots, c(51)$.

From Table 7, there is evidence of short-run unidirectional causality running from GDP to Total graduates and to all the variables representing the graduate characteristics (Male, Female, Arts, Science, postgraduates and undergraduates).

DISCUSSION

Our study disaggregates higher education by gender, discipline and award level in investigating the relationship with economic growth. In the findings, unidirectional causality was established from GDP to: male and female graduates, Arts and Science graduates, Post-graduate and undergraduates as well as total graduates. These findings demonstrate a reverse causality between higher education and economic growth. The evidence is contrary to empirical studies that have failed to

establish a causal relationship from economic growth to Higher education (Dudzeviciute, Simelyte & Liucvaitiene, 2018). It is more unlikely that the causal relationship from economic growth to higher education would be established in some studies (Ogunbunmi & Abiola, 2017; Kocourek & Nedomlelova, 2018) since they were based on methodological approaches that are not able to decompose the bi-causality of these variables. For example, the application of OLS and Panel data methodologies used to analyse the relationship between higher education and economic growth provide findings based on the choice of dependent variable. Consequently, economic growth is usually investigated as a function of higher education, among other determinants following theoretical literature. Nevertheless, the argument that higher education causes economic growth is certainly unrealistic since more graduates do not necessarily lead to faster growth of an economy (Hanushek, 2016). However, this does not completely rule out the importance of education as a whole in the growth of an economic but rather questions the importance of an added degree to economic growth.

The impact of economic growth on higher education is higher for males than females; graduates from science disciplines than Arts; and undergraduates than postgraduates. This is demonstrated in the findings by higher regression coefficient in the former attributes of higher education, when compared to the later. This evidence should not be surprising in light of government sponsorship for higher education in the country which is predominantly for undergraduate programs and science based disciplines. A higher proportion of males passing at lower levels of education in the country qualifies them to benefit more from both government and private support in higher education when compared to their counterparts the females. The majority of these males qualify and undertake science related disciplines.

In the short-run also, the estimation results reveal that higher education graduates had an insignificant impact on the economic growth of Uganda. These findings demonstrate a reverse causality between higher education and economic growth. The evidence is contrary to theoretical literature and many empirical studies that have established a causal relationship from higher education to economic growth (Solow, 1957; Mankiw et al., 1992). However, these findings are in agreement with previous studies in Ghana, Ethiopia, South Africa, Cote d'Ivoire and Indonesia (Nketiah-Amponsah, 2009; Borojo & Yushi, 2015; Malangeni & Phiri, 2018; Kouton, 2018; Rizal & Nurruhwati, 2018). The findings of this study could probably be due to the emphasis of quantity

of education, such as, increase in numbers of institutions or enrolments that might not contribute much to the economy rather than quality of education (Hanushek, 2016; Malangeni & Phiri, 2018). Therefore, this implies that relying on Uganda's higher education to attain short-run economic growth is currently a misplaced priority, which suggests that for short-run growth in Uganda, resources should be diverted to other levels of education and factors that improve basic skills, thereafter build upon them at higher education rather than focusing to expand higher education in terms of high numbers of universities or massive enrolments as a short term national goal.

This study evidences a long-run relationship between GDP and higher education graduates in Uganda from 1985 to 2017 based on the Johansen co-integration tests. The empirical findings of this study are similar with previous studies in Nigeria, Turkey, Malaysia, Greece, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Indonesia and Cote d'Ivoire (Babatunde & Adefabi, 2005; Beşkaya, Savaş, & Samlioglu, 2010; Shaihani et al., 2011; Pegkas & Tsamadias, 2014; Vijesandran & Vinayagathan, 2015; Muhamad, Sulaiman & Saputra, 2018; Kouton, 2018). The long-run relationship could possibly be attributed to production experience that is obtained later by graduates in the labour market. This study suggests that investment in higher education should be done to guarantee growth of the economy in the long-run.

The policy implication of the impact of higher education on economic in the long-run is that there should be adjustments in the policies, from short-run to long-run, if any impact is to be evidenced. Higher education should become a central target for future returns, and the next generation foundation, and that higher education should be a future predictor of economic growth. This reverse relationship implies that economic growth is important in obtaining growth of other sectors in the economy. This further suggests that as countries grow, their investments in the education sector also actually increase. This implies that as economy grows, there are more available resources to invest in education. Therefore, this calls for consideration from policy makers, as economic growth is an incentive for growth of the higher education sector

Conclusion

This study gives an endogenous perspective of the causal relationship between higher education graduates and economic growth of Uganda. It sheds light on the impact of the graduates' characteristics of gender, discipline and award level, on economic growth. The results confirm the role of GDP in the growth of the higher education sector, while the existence of a long-run but not

short-run effect of higher education on the growth of GDP. Disaggregating higher education into different categories confirms the impact of GDP on the growth of graduates of different characteristics; plus the insignificance of the reverse causality in the short-run. The impact of economic growth on higher education is higher for graduates who are males than females, those from science disciplines than Arts, and undergraduates than postgraduates. The Wald test also cited the vital role of GCF in linking these two variables.

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